

Crystallographic Pattern Analysis of Bagobo Tagabawa's Inabal Woven Fabric

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Abstract

This study analyzed the application of mathematical concepts in Bagobo Tagabawa's Inabal woven fabric. It identified geometric, symmetric, and crystallographic patterns. Researchers employed ex post facto analysis and analyzed mathematical patterns in the Inabal woven fabric. Researchers utilized the sample picture and investigated crystallographic patterns in the fabric using crystallographic codes for frieze patterns. Data analysis showed that geometric concepts are present in the Inabal woven fabric, such as points, lines, and shapes, such as circles, triangles, semi-circles, hexagons, and rhombuses. The fabric displays symmetry, such as translation, vertical and horizontal reflection, and rotation. Bagobo Tagabawa's Inabal woven fabric is a composition of different frieze pattern designs analyzed in light of the International Union of Crystallography. The Inabal woven fabric revealed a dominant frieze pattern - $pmm2$. Other frieze patterns found were $pm11$, $pmm1$, and $p111$, which only occurred once in the fabric. Further, it is recommended that educational institutions integrate educational experiences in analyzing mathematical patterns present in fabrics and other real-life objects. The use of Bagobo Tagabawa's Inabal woven fabric as a real-life example may be applied to learning geometric concepts in schools. Additionally, other researchers may conduct parallel studies to identify more mathematical concepts in other Mindanaoan fabrics. In conclusion, the research objectives have been effectively addressed by thoroughly analyzing patterns within the Bagobo Tagabawa community and their traditional textiles.

Keywords: *Bagobo Tagabawa's Inabal woven fabric, crystallographic pattern analysis, Mindanao patterns, Davao City, Philippines.*

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Introduction

Mathematics continues to inspire the conceptualization of clothing and fashion items, and over the past century its role in the fashion sector has expanded through advances in computation and manufacturing technologies. In the current landscape, mathematics provides theoretical and

computational tools for design and production while also fostering creativity, especially through the use of mathematical patterns for artistic appreciation and model development. Weaving, defined as the intertwining of vertical and horizontal yarns to create textile, reflects this connection between art and mathematics (Valera et al., 2020). In Indonesia, particularly in Java, ethnomathematics appears in Joglo houses through lines, angles, triangles, rectangles, quadrilaterals, congruency, and the Pythagorean theorem (Pramudita & Rosnawati, 2019). Likewise, bamboo crafts in the Muntuk community reveal woven motifs connected to Anyaman crafts and embedded mathematical ideas (Maryati & Prahmana, 2019). Ethnomathematics is especially relevant in the Philippines because its archipelagic nature has produced rich and diverse cultural heritage and practices (Libo-on, 2019). It also challenges the notion that mathematics is a universal phenomenon detached from culture (Irvan, 2023). Mathematical analysis of funeral textiles from indigenous communities in Northern Luzon found favored frieze groups and plane crystallographic groups that reflect beliefs and traditions (De Las Peñas & Salvador-Amores, 2016). In Southern Mindanao, one of the many cultural groups produced high-quality textiles, clothing, weapons, shields, and accessories decorated with colorful beadwork (Bunoan, n.d.). Among these cultural products is Inabal, a traditional abaca textile woven in the ikat style and dyed with vegetable and natural colors, once used as garments for ancestral royalty. Wearing these clothes carries multiple meanings, while the Inabal style reflects a complex taxonomy of abaca fabric that determines proper use according to gender, age, and other factors (Quizon, 2007; Quizon, 2000). Exploring mathematics within such traditions allows deeper understanding of the country's culture point by point (Libo-on, 2019). Hence, this study focuses on analyzing the patterns present in Inabal loom fabrics. Examining these handwoven fabrics is important not only for their beauty and captivating designs but also for the mathematical concepts they embody, linking cultural creations with mathematical understanding and real-world applications of geometry and pattern analysis.

Research Objectives

The study aims to engage students in the practical use of mathematical concepts such as weaving. Specifically, it seeks to achieve the following objectives:

1. to describe geometric concepts found in the Bagobo Tagabawa's Inabal woven fabric.
2. to identify symmetric analysis embedded in the Bagobo Tagabawa's Inabal woven fabric.
3. to analyze the crystallographic pattern included in the Bagobo Tagabawa's Inabal woven fabric.

Materials and Methods

The ex post facto analysis design and ethnomathematics are utilized in this research. Ethnomathematics is the study of how individuals from various cultural groups devise ways of describing and interpreting their surroundings in response to obstacles, struggles, and human survival efforts (D'Ambrosio et al., 2016). Ethnomathematics is used to seek answers to different geometric concepts. It is used to discover symmetry analyses. In addition, ethnomathematics demonstrated that mathematics is made up of many varied and unique cultural traditions, with an emphasis on indigenous mathematical concepts, techniques, and practices (Rosa & Orey, 2011). While ex post facto analysis is the analysis and manipulation of presented data, researchers used this to expose the different crystallographic patterns present in the Inabal woven fabric. This research utilized Bagobo Tagabawa's Inabal woven fabric. This means that this research did not use human participants. The *Inabal* fabric was used as a sample itself. The naming conversion from the International Union of Crystallography, referred to as the IUC notation, is used to distinguish among the seven frieze symmetry types.

- These names all begin with “p” followed by three characters.
- The first character is “m” if there is *vertical reflection*, 1 if none.
- The first character is “m” if there is *horizontal reflection*, “a” if there is *glide reflection*, 1 if none.
- The third is “2” if there is a *rotation* and 1 if there is none.

Results and Discussions

Geometric Concepts Found in Bagobo Tagabawa’s Inabal Woven Fabric

This section presents the geometric concepts found in Inabal Woven Fabric. Table 1 is characterized by nine patterns from the Inabal woven fabric. The presentation includes cropped images and their generated patterns. The unit cells that are identified by cutting a specific motif from the generated pattern are also introduced in this table. Generally, geometric concepts, including points, lines, and planes, are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. The Analysis of Patterns in Terms of Points, Lines, and Planes

Pattern	Cropped Image	Generated Pattern	Unit Cells	Point	Line	Plane
1						
2						
3						
4						
5						
6					No Line	
7						
8						
9						

Point. Each possible shape (for a given number of landmarks and dimensionality) corresponds to a single point in the shape space, and every point in the shape space corresponds to a particular shape

(Klingenberg, 2020). Point is an undefined concept in geometry, lacking dimensions such as length, width, or thickness—it's simply a tiny dot. Considering its simplicity, a point may generate complicated patterns akin to chaos. It goes beyond the fundamental classroom concept of a dot; in real-life situations, this seemingly small dot may expand into attractive forms and patterns. When closely examined, the woven cloth of Abra appears to be basic cloth but is really made up of a collection of points (Valera et al., 2020).

Table 1.1. Points in Bagobo Tagabawa's Inabal Woven Fabric

Pattern	Generated Patterns	Unit Cells	Points
1			
2			
3			
4			
5			
6			
7			

8			
9			

Table 1.1 displays various points observed in the Inabal woven fabric. By connecting these individual points, one can create straight lines, and these straight lines are what make the patterns in the Inabal woven fabric. The points are visible from the edges and vertices of the patterns. Therefore, it is safe to conclude that the Inabal woven fabric is composed of points, as shown in Table 1.1.

Line. A line is defined as a straight set of points that extends infinitely in opposite directions. It has no endpoints, thickness, or width, and it is considered to be one-dimensional because it only has length. Lines can be observed in the method of loom weaving in Abra, and before the thread gets introduced into the machine, it is modified in the weaving frame, placing the threads vertically to make parallel lines (Valera et al., 2020).

Table 1.2. Lines in Bagobo Tagabawa's Inabal Woven Fabric

Pattern	Generated Image	Unit Cell	Line
1			
2			
3			
4			

5			
6		No Line	
7			
8			
9			

Table 1.2 displays various lines observed in the Inabal woven fabric. By connecting these lines, one can create planes or patterns similar to what is found in Inabal woven fabric. These lines are essential elements in the examination and analysis of patterns found in Inabal woven fabric. However, not all patterns in the Inabal woven fabric have lines on them. This is evident in pattern 6 of the Inabal woven fabric. Therefore, there are lines present on the Inabal woven fabric, except for pattern 6.

Plane. A geometric pattern is formed by geometric shapes that are typically repeated in a given order in which new shapes or sub-shapes can emerge (Reis, 2023). A plane is a flat, two-dimensional surface that extends infinitely in all directions. Shapes change freely in the creative process, unlike symbols (Yu et al., 2023).

Table 1.3. Planes in Bagobo Tagabawa's Inabal Woven Fabric

Pattern	Generated Image	Plane	Plane Figure
1			

2			
3			
4			
5			
6			
7			
8			
9			

Table 1.3 presents planes identified within the concepts of geometry. The use and application of these geometric shapes form patterns that are visible in the Inabal woven fabric. As shown in Table 1.3, only one to two shapes are present in every pattern of the Inabal woven fabric. The most common shape in the Inabal woven fabric is the hexagon shape, which has six sides, followed by a semi-circle, a circle, a triangle, and then a rhombus. Similar shapes, such as hexagons and circles,

are observed in patterns 1, 3, and 6. All revealed shapes have similarities with each pattern, but the shape of the rhombus is only evident in pattern 4 and not in other patterns. Therefore, it is safe to say that shapes such as hexagons, semi-circles, circles, triangles, and rhombuses are present in the Inabal woven fabric.

Symmetries Found in Bagobo Tagabawa's Inabal Woven Fabric

This section presents the symmetries found in Inabal woven fabric. The symmetries are translation, vertical and horizontal reflection, and rotation. The presentation still includes the nine patterns with their cropped images, generated patterns, and unit cells.

Table 2. The Analysis of Patterns in Terms of Translation, Vertical and Horizontal Reflection, and Rotation

Pattern	Cropped Image	Generated Pattern	Unit Cells	Translation	Vertical Reflection	Horizontal Reflection	Rotation
1							
2						No Horizontal Reflection	No Rotation
3							
4							
5							
6							No Rotation

7					No Vertical Reflection	No Horizontal Reflection	No Rotation
8							
9							

Translation. A translation is a procedure that moves each point in the plane from one point to another in a specific direction, as described by a vector (De Las Peñas & Salvador-Amores, 2016). This alteration maintains the original shape and dimensions of the object, merely adjusting its location within the coordinate system or space. Weaved textiles from La Paz and San Juan exemplify translation, which refers to moving an item in a single direction without rotating or scaling the preimage (Valera et al., 2020).

Table 2.1. Translation in Bagobo Tagabawa's Inabal Woven Fabric

Pattern	Generated Image	Unit Cell	Translation
1			
2			
3			
4			

5			
6			
7			
8			
9			

Table 2.1 shows that translating a specific unit cell will produce a similar pattern. This is evident by sliding or moving the generated unit cell. Therefore, translation is evident by moving the unit cell in a specified direction horizontally, producing a similar pattern as seen in Table 2.1.

Vertical Reflection. The woven cloth in Abra has designs resembling frogs; when split vertically, it creates mirror images, and the line of symmetry on the second figure is created vertically at the middle of the pattern, resembling a diamond that causes the horses to reflect vertically (Valera et al., 2020). This process maintains the object's size and form while altering its alignment or orientation. Reflection transforms a plane's points into their mirror images along a fixed line known as the axis of reflection (De Las Peñas & Salvador-Amores, 2016). Reflections are extensively explored in geometry and linear algebra and are pivotal for grasping symmetry and shape transformations.

Table 2.2. Vertical Reflection in Bagobo Tagabawa's Inabal Woven Fabric

Pattern	Generated Image	Unit Cell	Vertical Reflection
1			
2			
3			

4			
5			
6			
7		No Vertical Reflection	
8			
9			

Table 2.2 shows that reflecting a specific unit cell will produce a similar pattern. This involves flipping the unit cell over a vertical line. As the patterns were reflected vertically, it was noticeable that similar mirrored patterns were produced. However, in pattern 7, no vertical reflection can be produced. This is evident because when the pattern is reflected, no other symmetrical pattern is produced. Therefore, it is safe to say that the patterns can produce symmetry through vertical reflection, aside from pattern 7 of the Inabal woven fabric.

Horizontal Reflection. In the woven fabric of Abra, the pattern is flipped horizontally, producing two identical images of the horses and diamond-like patterns (Valera et al., 2020). A horizontal reflection is a geometric change that mirrors a shape or object over a line, plane, or point, resulting in a flipped image. This process maintains the object's size and form while altering its alignment or orientation.

Table 2.3. Horizontal Reflection in Bagobo Tagabawa's Inabal Woven Fabric

Pattern	Generated Image	Unit Cell	Horizontal Reflection
1			
2			

3			No Horizontal Reflection
4			
5			
6			
7			No Horizontal Reflection
8			
9			

Table 2.3 shows that reflecting a specific unit cell will produce a similar pattern. This involves flipping the unit cell over a horizontal line. As the patterns were reflected horizontally, similar mirrored patterns were produced. However, in patterns 3 and 7, no horizontal reflection is produced. This is observed because when the pattern is reflected, no symmetry is produced. Therefore, patterns from Inabal woven fabric can produce symmetry through horizontal reflection, except for patterns 3 and 7.

Rotation. The particular sequence of a rotation refers to the sequence of rotations it must complete to return the plane to its original position (Alba et al., 2020). During this transformation, every point of the figure is rotated by a defined angle around the center, ensuring that the distances between points and the overall shape remain unchanged. The figure, which has a 180-degree rotation, highlights the distinctive form of the woven cloth's patterns by making it appear as though it is being rotated without changing its form (Valera et al., 2020). By rotating each unit cell 180 degrees, the symmetry of the pattern is formed.

Table 2.4. Rotation in Bagobo Tagabawa's Inabal Woven Fabric

Pattern	Generated Image	Unit Cell	Rotation
1			
2			No Rotation
3			
4			
5			
6			No Rotation
7			No Rotation

8			
9			

Table 2.4 shows that rotating a specific unit cell will produce a similar pattern. This is evident by turning or rotating the generated unit cell 180 degrees. As shown in table 2.4, by 180-degree rotation, the patterns produced are symmetrically mirrored. However, no rotation was found in patterns 2, 6, and 7 of the Inabal woven fabric. With this 180-degree rotation, patterns produced are symmetrical to the original motif but not applicable to some patterns of Inabal woven fabric, such as patterns 2, 6, and 7.

Frieze Patterns Found in Bagobo Tagabawa's Inabal Woven Fabric

This section presents the patterns found in Inabal Woven Fabric, analyzed using the International Union of Crystallography (IUC) notation. The presentation still includes the nine patterns with their cropped images, generated patterns, and unit cells.

Frieze Pattern. To analyze and classify one-dimensional periodic frieze patterns, one needs to be able to recognize the existence of the symmetries of each pattern (Bodner, 2007). A frieze pattern is a repetitive design that stretches infinitely along a linear axis. These patterns are analyzed for their symmetrical qualities and can be categorized into various groups according to their symmetry. They are defined by their consistent and recurring elements, which are shifted, mirrored, or rotated to form the complete pattern.

Table 3. The Analysis of Patterns using the Crystallographic Codes from the International Union of Crystallography (IUC) Notation

Pattern	Cropped Image	Generated Pattern	Frieze Pattern	Codes
1		pmm2		
2		pm11		
3		pmm2		
4		pmm2		

5		pmm2		
6		p1m1		
7		p111		
8		pmm2		
9		pmm2		

Based on the analysis performed, patterns are evident on the Inabal woven fabric. Table 3 shows the following frieze patterns with their designated codes. It was perceived that the code *pmm2*, from patterns 1, 3, 4, 5, 8, and 9 occurs repeatedly. This means that most of the motifs present in the Inabal woven fabric have translation, horizontal and vertical reflection, and rotation. However, codes such as *pm11*, *pmm1*, and *p111* are also evident. This means that there are patterns in the Inabal woven fabric that have no reflection and rotation.

Conclusions

The Inabal woven fabric is a composition of different frieze patterns. There are nine patterns in all. Based on the results of the study, it is concluded that the Inabal woven fabric is composed of points that are visible from the edges of the patterns. Lines are also present in the patterns of the Inabal woven fabric, except for pattern 6. Geometric shapes such as hexagons, semi-circles, circles, triangles, and rhombuses are also present in the Inabal woven fabric. Similar shapes, such as hexagons and circles, are observed repeatedly in patterns 1, 3, and 6. However, the rhombus is only evident in pattern 4. For symmetries, all patterns of the Inabal woven fabric can be moved through translation and still produce a similar pattern. Symmetrical patterns are also observed through vertical reflection. However, it is not evident in pattern 7 of the Inabal woven fabric. Horizontal reflections on patterns also produced symmetry, except for patterns 3 and 7. Similar patterns are also visible in the Inabal woven fabric through a 180-degree rotation. However, in patterns 2, 6, and 7, symmetries are not evident. For frieze patterns, it is concluded that *pmm2* is the most recurring pattern in the Inabal woven fabric. It is evident in the patterns 1, 3, 4, 5, 8, and 9. This means that these patterns have translation, vertical and horizontal reflection, and rotation. However, the codes *pm11*, *pmm1*, and *p111* occur only once. The code *pm11* implies that the pattern only has translation and vertical reflection. For code *pmm1*, the pattern has only translation and vertical and horizontal reflection. Lastly, for the code *p111*, the pattern only has translation. The research objectives have been effectively addressed through the thorough analysis of patterns within the Bagobo Tagabawa community and their traditional textiles. By identifying, documenting, and analyzing these patterns, we have gained valuable insights into the cultural, historical, and ecological contexts that shape the community's artistic expressions. This study not only contributes

to the preservation of cultural heritage but also provides a foundation for future research exploring the intricate relationship between environment, culture, and craftsmanship.

Recommendations

Commission on Higher Education (CHED) authorities may use this research to improve what they provide for the benefit of students and their educational experiences. They may also utilize this research as a tool for future projects and include the Mindanaoan pattern in the school's curriculum. Educational institutions could use the outcomes of this research to improve what they provide for the benefit and experience of students learning. They may also relate mathematics to art and academic fields. Instructors could apply loom weaving to practically apply their geometric ideas and symmetry analysis lessons. They can additionally use this as an exercise to help learners improve their talents, particularly their mathematical abilities, creativity, and craftsmanship. Students can also utilize such motivation to improve their comprehension of numerous mathematical concepts, particularly patterns and geometry. Further research may utilize several woven fabrics for better analysis and comparison of the results of each woven fabric. The focus should be on conducting a comparative analysis between the patterns observed in the surroundings of the Bagobo Tagabawa community and those found in their traditional loom-woven fabrics. This comparative study will shed light on the cultural significance and influences shaping their weaving traditions. By exploring similarities and differences between environmental motifs and textile designs, we can deepen our understanding of how local ecology and cultural heritage intersect.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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